

Developing Adaptive Calibration and Benchmarking Methods for 6G Performance Measurement

Implementation and Conclusions from 6G-SANDBOX

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Abstract— The flexibility inherent to the 6G space through its use of virtualized/Service Based Architecture (SBA) networks means that generated performance results can be more difficult to contextualize than previous generations. In this space, experimentation, either with the purpose of evaluating the appropriate integration of a new network device, system or software or targeting the assurance of application-demanding performance service levels, needs to be done in such a way to ensure that the assessment is performed uninfluenced by the actual dimensioning constraints of the underlying beyond 5G (B5G)/6G experimentation platform. This paper explores the development of an Adaptive Calibration methodology, which can be used to provide context to results in the 6G space so that to ensure platform agnosticism. Exemplary results of its application in the 6G-SANDBOX project, exploiting four (4) different and geographically dispersed experimentation platforms, are presented hereby. The methodology involves the establishment of a baseline environment which can be measured before the introduction of a device/system/software under test (SUT). The results of the baseline measurement can be compared to the results including the SUT to produce deltas in multiple KPIs. These deltas can then be used to provide context to results generated within a single platform or be used to compare multiple platforms. The use of this methodology within 6G-SANDBOX uncovered significant performance disparities between the partaking platforms related to virtualization methods, and it is currently being used to drive the platforms closer to parity, investigate the virtualization issues and quantify the performance of various components within each individual platform. In this regard, the application of the proposed methodology is proven substantial to increase confidence in the SUT assessment results performed over B5G/6G experimentation platforms.

Keywords—6G; Measurement Methodology; Calibration; Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); Experimentation Framework;6G SANDBOX Project;

I. INTRODUCTION

As we design new methods for measuring performance of devices in the 6G realm, a key challenge that appears is the rapid adoption of virtualized network components and Service Based Architecture (SBA) cellular networks [3][4][5][6]. This change in infrastructure gives 6G greater flexibility, but this flexibility comes at the cost of measurement consistency: as underlying components of a network are fluid and subject to change much

faster than in previous generations, they create a continuously changing environment from which it is impossible to establish a permanent baseline to measure from [7][8][9]. This also affects the reproducibility of any measured result, as the level of variability introduced by the virtualization process is currently unclear [2]. This is especially true for measurement that goes beyond pure functionality assessment and intends to quantify and compare network components in terms of their performance ceilings. This paper describes a 6G Adaptive Calibration methodology created to tackle this issue, that creates dynamic context for any generated result to ensure its impact is understood and can be compared against other results in a fair manner. Section II covers the background that led to the development, with Section III describing the underlying theory of the designed methodology. Section IV describes the implementation of the methodology, and the results gained thereof, with the discussion of said results and their implications being covered in Section V. Section VI discusses the conclusions drawn from the described efforts.

II. BACKGROUND

In previous generations, the need for such dynamism in the testing process did not exist. The more predefined nature of network infrastructure meant that the details of the testing environment were usually well understood and were not expected to significantly change. Therefore, testing methodologies could rely on data from previous tests to establish baselines and provide necessary contextualization to generated results. As mentioned previously, that is no longer the case, and the specific impetus for the development described in this paper is the ongoing work on the SNS JU STREAM-C Project 6G-SANDBOX [1][10]. This project involves the development of an EU-wide 6G testing infrastructure comprised of 4 platforms located in Athens, Berlin, Malaga and Oulu. Each platform possesses the ability to dynamically deploy “Trial Networks” – temporary experimentation networks synthesizing all necessary capabilities (access, core and networking components) to test new network and application systems, protocols or parameters. These Trial Networks make extensive use of the new paradigm of virtualized network components that define 6G, and as such the capabilities of each platform are exponentially increased. As the initial testing phase of 6G-SANDBOX began, two

requirements became clear. Firstly, there needed to be a way to “calibrate” each platform, ensuring that they are comparable on some level with some degree of reproducibility of results from one platform to the next. Secondly, due to the ever-changing nature of each platform, there needed to be a way to understand what each potential component at a given platform meant in terms of performance differential. These two considerations, which are inherently linked, are what motivated and informed the design of the Adaptive Calibration methodology.

The two considerations listed above compound on each other to make the nuanced understanding of gathered data from a 6G environment significantly more difficult. The core of the methodologies described in this paper designed to solve this issue is the dynamic measurement of baseline conditions. This means measuring the performance of the current network or environment before any System/Software/Device Under Test (SUT) is inserted or tested, and providing the user with this measurement to contextualize the measurements taken once the SUT is added. This process of dynamically measuring the baseline performance of a given environment for the purposes of contextualizing user results is referred to as the Calibration of a result within 6G-SANDBOX, and when Calibration is mentioned further on in this paper, this is what is meant.

III. METHODOLOGY DESIGN

The implementation of the Adaptive Calibration system can be split into two methods – the Intra Platform method and the Inter Platform method. The Intra Platform method describes the process of calibration and contextualization of results generated from modifications made on a single platform, be they new devices or just changes to the network. The Inter Platform method describes the process of calibration and contextualization of results by implementing the same Trial Network on different platforms. The Intra method is intrinsic, whereas the Inter method is extrinsic, with its use being a natural extension of the data the system generates despite it not being part of the design itself.

A. Intra Platform

The Intra Platform method is the main application of this methodology. In this case, results gathered from changes introduced to a network are automatically compared against results measured on the network without said changes applied. To facilitate this, a baseline environment is predefined. In 6G-SANDBOX, this is the concept of the Trial Network, but this can also be any baseline network where the SUT will be inserted to be evaluated. All necessary Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) must be initially measured on this baseline network. These results will serve three purposes. Firstly, they will be the basis for the contextualization of the SUT results performed later. Secondly, these results are checked against known results for this baseline to ensure that the baseline environment is still performing as expected with minimal deltas to previous test execution instances. Finally, these results can also be used for the Inter Platform Calibration, as described in Section III.B. Once the collection of the baseline measurements is complete, the SUT(s) can be inserted into the network. Since contextualization can only be performed on a per SUT basis, if the desired outcome is the contextualization of the outcomes of

separate SUTs, these must be tested separately. Once each SUT is inserted, the testing can be repeated, with the new results recorded. These results are combined with the baseline results, and the deltas can be identified, as a percentage, ratio, or absolute values. These deltas are the key output of the Adaptive Calibration system. With an understanding of the individual KPIs, the deltas can be used to describe the ways in which the SUT has impacted the baseline system, and the scale/relevance of this impact. Furthermore, the generated deltas between multiple different SUTs can themselves be compared, to understand how each SUT within the selection differs. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the entire functionality.

Figure 1: A block diagram illustrating the functionality of the Adaptive Calibration System

The entirety of this above-described process is designed with the intention of it being automated. When a test is initiated, the system will first run the test on the baseline environment, then insert the first SUT, repeat the test, insert the second SUT, repeat the test, and so on until results for all of the SUTs are generated. The user will then be presented with the deltas from each SUT to the baseline and between each SUT. This means that the entirety of the baseline environment and the capability for each SUT to be substituted into said environment must be set up beforehand. The frontloading of this configuration work means that the user will not be required to interact with the network configuration during the testing phase, reducing the amount of knowledge about the specific network infrastructure required and speeding up the process of generating and comparing results.

B. Inter Platform

As mentioned previously, the Inter Platform implementation is not a part of the automated methodology itself, but instead an extrapolation of the data generated by the methodology compare performance of “identical” baseline environments on different platforms. Specifically, the baseline measurement results which are used to provide context for the Intra Platform calibration, can also be used to calibrate multiple platforms using different underlying hardware implementations. By running the same tests on the same network topology on different hardware implementations, the deltas in performance between these implementations can be calculated, helping to understand intrinsic differences between different execution environments.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

This methodology was developed in the scope of the 6G-SANDBOX project, and the relevant implementations are ongoing exploiting the four (4) participating distinct B5G/6G platforms. Currently, the goal within 6G-SANDBOX is to create a universal baseline environment that can be used to perform both Inter and Intra platform calibration on all four platforms, internally referred to as the Reference Trial Network (RTN). In the Inter implementation, the RTN would be used to ensure each of the platforms could replicate a known network to a satisfactory level of similarity. This would ensure some level of capability parity between each platform. In the Intra implementation, the RTN could be used as a universal baseline for all potential network components in each platform. By recording the performance deltas for each in comparison with the RTN, they could be compared against each other contextually.

In the context of 6G SANDBOX, the RTN in its minimal formation is defined to be an open source 5G core (OPEN5GS) deployed in a Virtual Machine (VM) using the default hardware/performance parameters [13]. The performance of the RTN is measured using Keysight's LoadCore core testing tool, that is working in a wraparound configuration, emulating the Data Network (DN) and the Radio Access Network (RAN) components including User Equipment (UE) [14]. Each of these emulated components is installed in a separate Virtual Machine in the network with fixed and predefined hardware parameters. However, in the initial deployment of the RTN certain resource details had been left up to each platform's discretion, such as the hypervisor hosting the VMs and details of the interconnection infrastructure between each of the components.

A. Experimental Setup

With this initial RTN defined, work is shifted on running the measurement tests for the target KPIs and implementing the Adaptive Calibration methodology. The KPIs of interest have already been defined by 6G-SANDBOX and are based on 5G ITU [11], and in the initial testing campaign were as follows:

- **Peak Data Rate (PDR):** The maximum achieved data rate for one UE. Represents the peak performance of the system.
- **User Experienced Data Rate (UEDR):** The expected minimum baseline that any given UE in the system should expect. Defined as the 5th percentile throughput result.
- **Packet Loss Rate (PLR):** The rate of packets that did not reach either the DN or the UEs.
- **User Plane Latency (UPL):** The latency of transmission in the user plane.
- **User Plane Delay Deviation/Jitter (DD):** The amount of variance in the measured delays in the user plane.
- **Control Plane Latency (CPL):** The latency in the control plane, defined as the time taken for a UE to go from idle to a transmission state.

The measurement of these KPIs, with the exemption of PDR that is targeting a single peak value, were conducted with parallel UEs running, using sets typically involving from fourteen (14) to twenty (20) UEs.

B. Inter Platform Observations

As the testing phase of 6G-SANDBOX began ramping up, one of the prevailing assumptions was that the virtualisation insights of the RTN implementation would not have a significant impact on the observed performance given that basic computational resources allocation for the RTN had been commonly agreed. This is an expectation of SBA cellular networks, where underlying infrastructure varies across different implementations, but results are expected to be consistent due to the virtualisation layer being an equalising factor. Inter Platform Calibration was applied to test this hypothesis. The RTN was deployed by each platform, with a basic agreement on the resources allocated per Reference Trial Components (such as the number of vCPUs and memory allocated per VM), with more detailed parameterisation of the virtualisation left up to the platform coordinators (such as the hypervisor used, settings for overprovisioning, physical host characteristics). Then, three (3) main test cases were performed, collecting each of the above mentioned KPIs. The first test case ran TCP traffic in both the uplink (UE to DN) and downlink (DN to UE) directions, collecting data for the PDR, UEDR and PLR KPIs. The second test case ran UDP traffic in both the uplink and downlink directions, collecting data for the UPL and DD KPIs. The final test case also ran UDP traffic in both directions but also introduced a large number of requests for cycling the UEs between an idle and active state, loading the control plane. As such, the data was used for the CPL KPI. Once results at each platform were collected, the overall/average best performing platform for each KPI was identified, and deltas between this platform and the others for each KPI were calculated on this basis. These deltas can be seen in Tables I - VI. The values in green indicate performance above the baseline.

TABLE I. INITIAL AVERAGE PDR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	80,76%	78,47%
Berlin	22,69%	57,65%
Malaga	Baseline	Baseline
Oulu	36,70%	58,80%

TABLE II. INITIAL AVERAGE UEDR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	0,59%	40,75%
Berlin	0,4%	0,71%
Malaga	Baseline	Baseline
Oulu	0,69%	0,75%

TABLE III. INITIAL AVERAGE PLR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	Baseline	Baseline
Berlin	3,42%	49,74%
Malaga	6,89%	47,43%
Oulu	11,99%	124,41%

TABLE IV. INITIAL AVERAGE UPL DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	5.489,27%	18.394,45%
Berlin	28,29%	213,39%
Malaga	9,4%	43,83%
Oulu	Baseline	Baseline

TABLE V. INITIAL AVERAGE DD DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	9950,00%	4066,67%
Berlin	125,00%	183,33%
Malaga	150,00%	266,67%
Oulu	Baseline	Baseline

TABLE VI. INITIAL AVERAGE CPL DELTAS

Platform	Average Delta
Athens	16,69%
Berlin	Baseline
Malaga	3,10%
Oulu	6,54%

As is obvious from these tables, it is clear that the simple act of working in the virtualisation layer is not enough to alleviate differences in performance. The deltas for practically all of the KPIs show extreme values that border on being essentially incomparable. The level of disparity shown in these results came as a surprise to both the platforms and the testing partners within 6G-SANDBOX, and it was decided to further apply Inter platform calibration and investigate further.

In this second round of testing, the standardisation of the RTN implementation was increased. This time, all components would be deployed through Open Nebula as a hypervisor and significant aspects of the network infrastructure would now be standardised between each deployment through the use of 6G SANDBOX's virtual network infrastructure [18]. This meant that in theory the only differences between platform implementations now were physical: servers, switches, physical wire connections, etc. The deltas for measurements conducted with this new setup can be seen in Tables VII – XII.

TABLE VII. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE PDR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	49,34%	39,24%
Berlin	Baseline	Baseline
Malaga	37,25%	9,46%
Oulu	8,58%	3,82%

TABLE VIII. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE UEDR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	57,97%	51,39%
Berlin	Baseline	Baseline
Malaga	35,59%	17,7%
Oulu	53,82%	52,02%

TABLE IX. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE PLR DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	45,79%	42,6%
Berlin	7,09%	13,44%
Malaga	Baseline	Baseline
Oulu	25,67%	16,4%

TABLE X. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE UPL DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	21,4%	4,97%
Berlin	31,38%	5,85%
Malaga	56,73%	35,39%
Oulu	Baseline	Baseline

TABLE XI. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE DD DELTAS

Platform	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	30%	5,41%
Berlin	Baseline	Baseline
Malaga	26,67%	18,92%
Oulu	16,67%	10,81%

TABLE XII. IMPROVED IMPLEMENTATION AVERAGE CPL DELTAS

Platform	Average Delta
Athens	0%
Berlin	0%
Malaga	Baseline
Oulu	0%

The difference between the two sets of results is clear; while deltas still exist, the changes made to the implementation have reduced deltas across the board. The identification of the issues in the first dataset/implementation leading to the changes in the RTN implementation and the second, improved dataset are a direct result of the implementation of the Adaptive Calibration method and would have been much more difficult to identify otherwise, especially considering the large number of KPIs and the variety in implementation choices made by each of the platforms. However, even with a significant amount of the virtualisation layer parameters unified, the deltas for certain KPIs are too large for results to be considered replicable. This was a significant development, and the ramifications of this are further elaborated on in Section V. For 6G-SANDBOX, the next step in this process will be to further identify issues or areas where greater parity can be introduced, run more tests, and continuously calibrate the platforms until the deltas reach acceptable levels.

C. Intra Platform Observations

As well as the work done to analyse the level of parity between each of the platforms with a common RTN, tests were also done

to investigate the effects of different components within each of the platforms themselves, implementing the Intra Platform calibration methods described above. In this case, the component that was changed was the type/configuration of the core used, defining the different Trial Networks that can be supported by each platform. These other configurations would be adaptively calibrated against the initial Open5GS Reference configuration to understand the performance differences. Tables XIII – XVIII show some example results for the Berlin platform, while similar results exist for both Athens and Malaga platforms.

In the Tables that follow, the RTN is compared with Trial Network “Config 2” (Open5GCore on an ESXi hypervisor) and Trial Network “Config 3” (Open5GCore on an OpenNebula hypervisor) [15][16][17].

TABLE XIII. AVERAGE PDR DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Reference	Baseline	Baseline
Config 2	30,82%	20,62%
Config 3	110,59%	84,54%

TABLE XIV. AVERAGE UEDR DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Reference	Baseline	Baseline
Config 2	2,8%	0,14%
Config 3	2,8%	4,64%

TABLE XV. AVERAGE PLR DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Reference	Baseline	Baseline
Config 2	100%	100%
Config 3	100%	100%

TABLE XVI. AVERAGE UPL DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Reference	Baseline	Baseline
Config 2	99,76%	99,91%
Config 3	3,12%	50,27%

TABLE XVII. AVERAGE DD DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Reference	Baseline	Baseline
Config 2	99,92%	99,96%
Config 3	39,02%	43,07%

TABLE XVIII. AVERAGE CPL DELTAS FOR ALL 3 BERLIN CONFIGURATIONS

Configuration	Average Delta
Reference	Baseline
Config 2	3,85%
Config 3	3,85%

As we can see, Intra Platform Calibration shows us that Configs 2 and 3 perform better than the Reference almost across

the board, and we can investigate the data in more depth to elucidate more detailed insights. For example, Configs 2 and 3 both increase the UEDR in the uplink direction by the same amount, but Config 2 actually decreases it in the downlink direction, while Config 3 increases it. These results would then be compared against expectations to draw conclusions about each of the SUTs. This level of insight is available for all measured KPIs and drastically increases the value of the measurement data.

V. DISCUSSION AND INSIGHTS

The development of the Adaptive Calibration system came about as a way to improve the contextualization and legibility of results within 6G-SANDBOX, and while this was achieved, it is clear now that this system when fully implemented and automatized is capable of much more. Through the use of inter-platform calibration, we were able to fully understand just how much variability there was in the setups of all the different platforms, despite them being ostensibly “the same”. This goes directly against the belief that SBA networks through the employment of virtualization would be able to negate issues regarding hardware parity and enable test reproducibility across multiple environments. The inter platform calibration efforts showed how significant the impact of different hypervisors and network infrastructure could be, and although the second set of results are better, they still are not at the expected level of reproducibility. Further standardization might be necessary to get the deltas down to acceptable levels, although that begs the question of what the functionality of virtualization is if its key benefits have to be removed in order to ensure reliability of data.

When looking at 6G-SANDBOX specifically, while the goal is not to have four identical platforms, achieving platform parity is important for two main reasons. Firstly, it allows for the creation of a performance/health test for a prospective platform: a platform should be able to run the RTN in a given configuration and expect to see results with deltas in a given range. This ensures that on some level that platform is able to match the capabilities of all of the others. This calibration can also be used to ensure that a platform remains “healthy”; despite any upgrades and changes, its performance when implementing the RTN should fall within specified delta windows. Secondly, ensuring some level of parity allows for the possibilities of tests conducted on one platform to be repeated on another. Test reproducibility is a key question in SBA/virtualized networks, so if parity can be assured to a certain level of delta, differences in collected results between two platforms can be investigated fairly without the potential risk of platform disparity being the cause of said differences.

Zooming in to look at each platform in a vacuum, the Intra Platform calibration implementations allowed us to understand in greater depth the differences between different components and configurations. While such a system might not be necessary in a situation where few KPIs were being measured, 6G-SANDBOX is being designed to be able to produce many dozens of KPIs at once for a given test campaign. Understanding differences in performance once this level of dimensionality is introduced is no longer as straightforward. A change in configuration could lead to an improvement in one KPI but a

decrease in others, without full visibility of this it would be impossible to make conclusions about the impacts of these changes. The use of the intra platform calibration allows these impacts to be understood to a greater degree, and for more informed choices to be made. Instead of “Configuration A is better than Configuration B”, we can say “Configuration A sees a 47% increase in the PDR to Configuration B, at the cost a 9% worsening of the CPL and a 11% worsening of the DD”. This mindset can be scaled up to large sets of KPIs, where many-dimensional sets of deltas can be produced to accurately describe the effect of a component on a known environment. This description can then be used to potentially predict the effects of said component on a different virtualized environment, and if these effects do not follow the expected pattern, the reasons for the disparity can be investigated. More detailed insights can be found in 6G-SANDBOX Deliverable 5.3 [12].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The development of this Adaptive Calibration methodology has led to significant positive impacts for 6G-SANDBOX and the field of 6G testing in general. Firstly, it is clear that this methodology allows for a very large amount of KPIs to be analyzed at once and analyzed within a relevant context. By tying the KPIs to their results in a baseline environment, we can circumvent the inherent issue of the high level of dynamism in virtualized networks and remove a lot of the guesswork from results analysis, allowing for conclusions to be drawn from larger sets of data much easier. The systematic application of this baseline-based testing means that as long as the baseline is maintained, results from many different SUTs can be compared without the need for resource intensive retesting or designing of new test cases for the specific purpose. The implementation within 6G-SANDBOX itself lead to discovery of the weaknesses of virtualization in terms of ensuring platform parity/agnosticism and enabling result reproducibility. The level of result disparity observed was unprecedented, and lead to significant changes in the implementation methods for trial networks within 6G-SANDBOX. This would not have been possible without the implementation of the Adaptive Calibration methodology and the in-depth information it provides.

The next steps are the automation of the process and the increase in the available KPIs. Currently the running of the calibration and actual test and the computing of the deltas are done separately, but the goal is for all of this to be done automatically when a test campaign is run for a given SUT. The fact that the implementation of the system has already led to impactful results is extremely promising; allowing this to be done smoothly and automatically will make the process even smoother and allow for the analysis of even larger amounts of KPIs. We believe that this methodology is uniquely suited to the high demands of testing in the 6G space, and that it allows

for a level of insight that leads to better and more informed development of 6G technologies.

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